

K/100 g, and 1.2 ppm available Zn. The FYM contained 1.8% N and 0.45 ppm total P. FYM, all P and K, and 35 kg N/ha were applied basally; the remaining N was topdressed at panicle initiation. Grain yield was computed at 14% moisture.

No significant pest or disease damage or water stress occurred during crop development. All fertilizer treatments increased yield significantly (see table). Mean yield from plots given FYM alone was 20% higher than check plots. Supplementing FYM with extra N had no effect. FYM plus P significantly increased yield 18% over FYM alone. Yields with FYM supplemented with

N+P and from plots fertilized with N+P or N+P+K only did not differ significantly from yields with FYM+P.

The results indicate that utilization of nitrogen in FYM may be seriously limited by inadequate soil P. In Wangdiphodrang-Punakha, soil analyses now show that available P levels are generally low (less than 10 ppm). Available K and other plant nutrients appear to be adequate. These preliminary results suggest that in a region where use of inorganic fertilizer is very low but use of FYM is routine, more benefit could be obtained from supplementing FYM with P. □

Effect of FYM supplemented with N and P on yield of IR36. CARD, Wangdiphodrang, Bhutan, 1986.

FYM ^b (t/ha)	Fertilizer treatment ^a			Grain yield ^c (t/ha)
	N (kg/ha)	P (kg/ha)	K (kg/ha)	
0	0	0	0	4.8 c
7.5	0	0	0	5.8 b
7.5	35	0	0	5.3 bc
7.5	0	50	0	6.9 a
7.5	35	50	0	7.0 a
0	75	50	0	6.6 a
0	75	50	40	6.9 a
	CV (%)			4.5

^a N as urea, P as single superphosphate, K as muriate of potash. ^b Fresh weight. ^c Mean separation in a column by DMRT at the 5% level.

Phosphorus requirements in a rice - wheat cropping system

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We studied P requirements of rice grown in sequence with wheat in the field 1983 to 1987. Different combinations of P level (0, 13, and 26 kg P/ha) and P application (applying P to rice alone, wheat alone, or both rice and wheat) were laid out in a randomized block design with 4 replications.

At the beginning of the experiment in 1983, the soil (sandy loam, Typic Ustochrept) had pH 8.1, 0.29% organic C, and 14.5 kg Olsen's P/ha. All plots received 120 kg N and 23 kg K/ha. All

Influence of P on rice yield in a rice - wheat cropping system. Punjab, India, 1983-87.

P (kg/ha)		Grain yield (t/ha)					
Rice	Wheat	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	Mean 1984-87
0	0	7.4	5.7	6.2	6.4	5.6	6.0
13	0	7.3	6.8	7.2	8.4	8.4	7.7
26	0	7.5	6.9	7.2	8.4	8.6	7.8
0	13	7.5	6.0	6.5	7.2	6.8	6.6
0	26	6.8	6.0	6.5	7.3	7.6	6.8
13	13	7.1	6.7	7.4	8.3	8.5	7.7
13	26	7.5	6.8	7.2	8.4	8.6	7.8
26	13	7.0	6.8	7.1	8.3	8.5	7.7
26	26	7.5	6.6	7.1	7.9	7.4	7.2
LSD (0.05)		ns	0.7	0.4	0.9	0.7	0.7

P and K and 1/3 N were applied before transplanting. The remaining N was applied at 21 d and 42 d after transplanting.

Rice responded significantly to direct application of up to 13 kg P/ha (see

table). Rice grown on the residue of 25 kg P/ha applied to the preceding wheat showed no response. Increasing P to 26 kg/ha for both rice and wheat slightly depressed rice yield. □

Effect of two phosphorus sources with or without azolla incorporation on rice yield in the Senegal River valley

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We compared a soluble-type P (triple superphosphate with 45% P₂O₅) and a natural type P (aluminum phosphate

Soil analysis. Fanaye P4 (Paleustollic Torrerts), Fanaye Station, Senegal.

pH		Texture ^a	Clay (%)	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Organic matter ^b (%)	CEC ^c (meq/100 g)	Available P BRAY II (ppm)	Total P ^d (ppm)	Adsorbed P ^e at 0.2 ppm P in the soil solution (µg P/g of soil)
Soil:water (1:1)	KCl 1 N									
6.2	4.4	Clay	46.5	29.9	23.6	0.35	31.26	1.50	240	330

^a Bouyoucos method. ^b Walkley - Black method. ^c Cobaltihexamine method (Orsini et Remy 1976). ^d Perchloric acid digestion. ^e Fox and Kamprath method (1970).

with 34% P₂O₅). We also evaluated the influence of azolla incorporation on assimilation of P by rice.

The trial for four consecutive cropping seasons was conducted on a fine clayey soil Paleustollic Torrerts (see